

ISSN 0976 559X

वागीश्वरी

संस्कृतविभागीया विज्ञ-वीक्षिता वार्षिकी शोधपत्री

संख्या-१५

VĀGĪŚVARĪ

Peer Reviewed Multilingual Research Journal

Volume - XV

Department of Sanskrit
Assam University, Silchar
2020

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The position of the Dakṣiṇāgni in the Sacrificial ground according to the Boudhāyana Śulvasūtra

Milan Barman*

Agni is the predominating and pervading authority of all the srauta sacrifices. The Śulvasūtras have given the construction rules of sacrificial altars. The Ṛgveda Saṁhitā mentions the three Agni and it implies the three sacred Agni: Gārhapatya, Āhavanīya and Dakṣiṇāgni.¹ In the Brāhmaṇa literature, these three fires have also been mentioned, and they are the most important for the performance of Śrauta sacrifices. The Śrauta sutras give detailed, subtly accurate and vivid descriptions of many sacrifices which were performed in ancient times. All the Śrauta sacrifices are to be performed in these three fireplaces.

The Gārhapatya Agni is located in the centre of the fire-hall.² The centre of the Gārhapatya Agni should be on the pṛṣṭhyā, the central east-west line of the fire-hall. This Agni should be circular and its diameter is 27 aṅgulas³ and the area is one square aratni⁴. The centre of the Āhavanīya Agni should also be on the pṛṣṭhyā, and it should be located towards the east from the Gārhapatya Agni. Its shape is square, and each side being 24 aṅgulas long. The area of the Agni should be one square aratni. The location of the Dakṣiṇāgni is concerned that of the Āhavanīya and Gārhapatya Agnis. The shape of this Agni is semi-circular. Its diameter should be $38\frac{1}{4}$ aṅgulas and area are is one square aratni.

The Dakṣiṇāgni is called so as it makes the sacrificer attain the Dakṣiṇā (supreme) state or this Agni is installed in the southern side of the sacrificial

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1 RV 2.36.4, आ वक्षि देवाँ इह विप्र यक्षि चोशन्होतर्नि षदा योनिषु त्रिषु ।
प्रति वीहि प्रस्थितं सोम्यं मधु पिबाम्नीध्रात्तव भागस्य तृप्नुहि ॥

2 Boudhāyana Śulvasūtra.20.18 “.....देवयजनेऽगारं वा विमितं वा कारितं भवति ।मध्ये गार्हपत्यस्यायतनं कुर्वन्ति ।”

3 BSS- I.4-5 The unit aṅgula is defined as equal to the length of fourteen aṅgus or it consists of thirty-four tilas (sesame grain) when placed in contact with each other along their broad sides

4 BSS- I.16 The unit an aratni is contains of 24 aṅgulas

enclosure.⁵ This Agni also known as Anvāharyapacana because on it is cooked the rice with Piṇḍ-pitṛyajña which is performed on the new moon⁶ or on it the offering material is cooked.⁷

The position of the Dakṣiṇāgni is described in three different ways in the Boudhāyana Śulvasūtra.

Calculations:

Let, A = Āhavanīya, G = Gārhapatya and D = Dakṣiṇāgni.

Method – I

Boudhāyana suggested that, to locate the Dakṣiṇāgni, make three squares of side one-third of the distance between the Āhavanīya and the Gārhapatya fires such that the squares touch each other. The place of the Gārhapatya is in the North-West corner (śronī) of the Western square, the place of the Anvāharyapacana or Dakṣiṇāgni is in the South-East corner (aṁsa) of the same square; the place of the Āhavanīya is in the North-East corner of the eastern square.⁸ Similar rules, though worded differently, are discussed in both the Āpastamba Śulvasūtra⁹ and Kātyāyana Śulvasūtra¹⁰.

Let the distance between the Āhavanīya and the Gārhapatya is X.

So, the given,

$$AG = X; AN = \frac{X}{3}; ND = \frac{2X}{3}$$

$$AD = \sqrt{AN^2 + ND^2} = \sqrt{\frac{X^2}{9} + \frac{4X^2}{9}} = \frac{\sqrt{5}X}{3}$$

$$DM = \frac{X}{3}$$

⁵ Jivanananda, Dharmasāstra saṅgraha, p.603

⁶ Taittiriya Brāhmaṇa 1.1.10, Manusmṛhitā. 3.123

⁷ Quoted by Śabara on Jaiminī 12.2.3

⁸ BŚS I.67 “आयामतृतीयेन त्रीणि चतुरस्राणि अनुचीनानि कारयेद् अपरस्योत्तरस्याङ्श्रोण्यां गार्हपत्यस्तस्यैव दक्षिणेऽङ्गुष्ठाहाहार्यपचनः पूर्वस्योत्तरेऽङ्गुष्ठाहाहार्यपचनः
इति ॥”

⁹ ĀŚS “दक्षिणत पुरस्ताद्विद्वितीयदेशे गार्हपत्यस्य नेदीयसि दक्षिणामनेर्विज्ञयते ।”

¹⁰ KŚS “अपि वाऽन्तरिभागोनया रज्ज्वा पूर्वदिशि समचतुरस्रं कृत्वा श्रोण्यामग्निः ।”

$$\frac{AD}{DM} = \frac{\frac{\sqrt{5}X}{3}}{\frac{X}{3}} = \sqrt{5}$$

$$GD = \sqrt{DM^2 + MG^2} = \sqrt{\frac{X^2}{9} + \frac{X^2}{9}} = \frac{\sqrt{2}X}{3}$$

$$\frac{GD}{DM} = \frac{\frac{\sqrt{2}X}{3}}{\frac{X}{3}} = \frac{\sqrt{2}X}{3} \times \frac{3}{X} = \sqrt{2}; \quad \frac{AG}{DM} = \frac{X}{\frac{X}{3}} = 3$$

$$\therefore \frac{AD}{GD} = \frac{\sqrt{5}X}{3} \times \frac{3}{\sqrt{2}X} = \frac{\sqrt{5}}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Method - II

In this method, Boudhāyana suggested that, divide the length between Āhavanīya and Gārhapaty Aagni either into five or six equal parts and added extra sixth or seventh part with it according to division what is preferred. Next, divide the whole length into three equal parts and make a mark at the end of the second part from the eastern side of a cord. Fasten the two ties of the cord to pegs at Āhavanīya and Gārhapaty and stretch the cord towards the south by the mark and a pole fixed at the mark where it reached. This is the place of the Dakṣiṇāgni.¹¹

(a) After adding the extra sixth parts (BŚS I.68)

Let the distance between the Āhavanīya and the Gārhapaty is X.

So,

$$\begin{aligned} MG &= \frac{GD^2 - AD^2 + AG^2}{2AG} = \frac{\left(\frac{7}{18}X\right)^2 - \left(\frac{7}{9}X\right)^2 + X^2}{2X} \\ &= \frac{177}{2 \times 324} X = 0.27314X. \end{aligned}$$

$$DM = \sqrt{DG^2 - MG^2}$$

¹¹ BŚS I.68 “अपि वा गार्हपत्याहवनीययोरन्तरालं पंचधा षोढा वा संभुज्य षष्ट्यसप्तमं वा भागमागन्तुकमुपसमस्य समं त्रैधं विभज्य पूर्वस्मादन्त्याद् द्वयोर्भागयोर्लक्षणं करोति। गार्हपत्याहवनीययोरन्तौ नियम्य लक्षणेन दक्षिणापायम्य लक्षणेन दक्षिणापायम्य लक्षणे शङ्कुं निहन्ति तद् दक्षिणाग्नेरायतनं भवति ॥”

$$= \sqrt{\left(\frac{7}{18}X\right)^2 - (0.27314X)^2}$$

$$= 0.27682X.$$

$$AM = AG - MG = X - 0.27314X$$

$$= 0.72686X.$$

$$\therefore \frac{AD}{DM} = \frac{\left(\frac{7}{9}X\right)}{0.27682X} = \frac{0.77777X}{0.27682X} = 2.80956$$

$$= \sqrt{7.89413}$$

$$\frac{GD}{DM} = \frac{\left(\frac{7}{18}X\right)}{0.27682X} = \frac{0.38888X}{0.27682X} = 1.40481$$

$$= \sqrt{1.97349}$$

$$\frac{AG}{DM} = \frac{X}{0.27682X} = 3.61245$$

$$\frac{AD}{GD} = \frac{\frac{7}{9}X}{\frac{7}{18}X} = 2$$

(b) After adding the extra seventh parts (BŚS I.68)

$$MG = \frac{GD^2 - AD^2 + AG^2}{2AG}$$

$$= \frac{\left(\frac{8}{21}X\right)^2 - \left(\frac{16}{21}X\right)^2 + X^2}{2X}$$

$$= 0.28231X.$$

$$DM = \sqrt{DG^2 - MG^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{\left(\frac{8}{21}X\right)^2 - (0.28231X)^2}$$

$$= X\sqrt{0.06543}$$

$$= 0.25579X.$$

$$AM = AG - MG$$

$$= X - 0.28231X = 0.71769X.$$

$$\therefore \frac{AD}{DM} = \frac{\left(\frac{16}{21}X\right)}{0.25579X} = \frac{0.76190}{0.25579X} = 2.97861 = \sqrt{8.87211}$$

$$\frac{GD}{DM} = \frac{\left(\frac{8}{21}X\right)}{0.25579X} = \frac{0.38095X}{0.25579X} = 1.48930 = \sqrt{2.21801}$$

$$\frac{AG}{DM} = \frac{X}{0.25579X} = 3.90945$$

$$\frac{AD}{GD} = \frac{\frac{16}{21}X}{\frac{8}{21}X} = 2$$

Method - III

In this method, Boudhāyana says - the measure between the Āhavanīya and the Gārhapatya Agni is increased by its fifth, the whole of it is divided into five parts, and a mark is given at the end of the second part from the western extremity. With two ties fastened to the two ends of the east-west line (representing the distance between the two fires), the cord is stretched to the south by the mark and a pole fixed at the mark. This is the place of the Dakṣiṇāgni.¹²

Let the distance between the Āhavanīya and the Gārhapatya is X.

$$MG = \frac{GD^2 - AD^2 + AG^2}{2AG} = \frac{\left(\frac{2}{5}X\right)^2 - \left(\frac{4}{5}X\right)^2 + X^2}{2X}$$

¹²

BŚS I.69 “अपि वा प्रमाणं पंचमेन वर्धयेत् तत्सर्वं पञ्चधा संभुज्यापरस्मादन्त्याद् द्वयोर्भागयोर्लक्षणं करोति पृष्ठयान्तयोः पाशौ प्रतिमुच्य लक्षणेन दक्षिणापायम्य लक्षणे शङ्कुं निहन्ति तद् दक्षिणाग्नेरायतनं भवति ॥”

$$= \frac{\frac{4}{25}X^2 - \frac{16}{25}X^2 + X^2}{2X} = \frac{13}{50}X$$

$$= 0.26X$$

$$DM = \sqrt{DG^2 - MG^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{\left(\frac{2}{5}X\right)^2 - (0.26X)^2}$$

$$= 0.30397X.$$

$$AM = AG - MG = X - 0.26X = 0.74X.$$

$$\frac{AD}{DM} = \frac{\left(\frac{4}{5}X\right)}{0.30397X} = \frac{0.8X}{0.30397X} = 2.63183 = \sqrt{6.92652}$$

$$\frac{GD}{DM} = \frac{\left(\frac{2}{5}X\right)}{0.30397X} = \frac{0.4X}{0.30397X} = 1.31591 = \sqrt{1.733}$$

$$\frac{AG}{DM} = \frac{X}{0.30397X} = 3.28979$$

$$\therefore \frac{AD}{GD} = \frac{\frac{4}{5}X}{\frac{2}{5}X} = 2$$

The three different methods of Boudhāyana Śulvasūtra, the first method show that the Dakṣiṇāgni is exactly on the south-east direction with reference to Gārhapatya and the ratio is $\sqrt{2} : \sqrt{5}$. And the second and third methods show that the Dakṣiṇāgni is not exact towards the south-east direction and the ratio is 1 : 2. So far the discussion we can say the distances between Āhavanīya and Dakṣiṇāgni is $\sqrt{5}$ and Gārhapatya and Dakṣiṇāgni is $\sqrt{2}$ and the Dakṣiṇāgni should be present towards the south-east direction with reference to Gārhapatya Agni.

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